

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 148

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 148

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>1 Praise the LORD! Praise the LORD from the heavens; Praise Him in the heights!</p> <p>2 Praise Him, all His angels; Praise Him, all His hosts!</p> <p>3 Praise Him, sun and moon; Praise Him, all stars of light!</p> <p>4 Praise Him, highest heavens, And the waters that are above the heavens!</p> <p>5 Let them praise the name of the LORD, For He commanded and they were created. 6 He has also established them forever and ever; He has made a decree which will not pass away.</p>	<p>הִלְלוּ יְהוָה אֱת־יְהוָה מִן־ הַשָּׁמַיִם הִלְלוּהוּ בַמְרוֹמִים : 2 הִלְלוּהוּ כָל־מַלְאָכָיו הִלְלוּהוּ כָל־ צָבָאוֹ [צָבָאוֹ : 3] הִלְלוּהוּ שֶׁמֶשׁ וְיָרֵחַ הִלְלוּהוּ כָל־כּוֹכָבֵי אֹרֶךְ : 4 הִלְלוּהוּ שָׁמַי הַשָּׁמַיִם וְהַמַּיִם אֲשֶׁר אִמְעַל הַשָּׁמַיִם : 5 יְהִלְלוּ אֶת־שֵׁם יְהוָה כִּי הוּא צִוָּה וַיִּבְרָאוּ : 6 וַיַּעֲמִידֵם לָעֵד לְעוֹלָם תָּקִינְתָן וְלֹא יֵעָבֹר : 7 הִלְלוּ אֱת־יְהוָה מִן־ הָאָרֶץ תַּנִּינִים וְכָל־תְּהוֹמוֹת : 8 אֲשֶׁר וּבְרָד שֶׁלֵּג וְקִיטּוֹר רוּחַ סְעָרָה עֹשֶׂה דְבָרוֹ : 9 הַתְּהוֹרִים וְכָל־גְּבָעוֹת עֵץ פְּרוֹי וְכָל־אֲרָזִים : 10 הַתְּהִיָּה וְכָל־בְּהֵמָה רֹמֵשׁ וְצִפּוֹר כָּנָף : 11 מְלָכֵי־אֲרֶץ וְכָל־לְאֻמִּים שָׂרִים וְכָל־שֹׁפְטֵי אֲרֶץ : 12 בַּחֲוָרִים וְגַם־ בַּתּוֹלוֹת זְקֵנִים עִם־נְעָרִים : 13 יְהִלְלוּ אֶת־שֵׁם יְהוָה כִּי־נִשְׁגַּב שָׁמַי לְבָדוֹ הוֹדוּ עַל־אֲרֶץ וּשְׁמַיִם : וַיִּרְם קֶרֶן אֶלְעֲמוֹ תְהַלֵּה לְכָל־ חַסִּידָיו לְבְנֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל עִם־קָרְבוֹ הִלְלוּ־יְהוָה :</p>
<p>7 Praise the LORD from the Earth, Sea monsters and all deeps;</p> <p>8 Fire and hail, snow and clouds; Stormy wind, fulfilling His word;</p> <p>9 Mountains and all hills; Fruit trees and all cedars;</p> <p>10 Beasts and all cattle; Creeping things and winged fowl;</p> <p>11 Kings of the Earth and all peoples; Princes and all judges of the Earth;</p> <p>12 Both young men and virgins; Old men and children.</p> <p>13 Let them praise the name of the LORD, For His name alone is exalted; His glory is above Earth and Heaven.</p> <p>14 And He has lifted up a horn for His people, Praise for all His godly ones; <i>Even</i> for the sons of Israel, a people near to Him. Praise the LORD!</p>	<p>יְהִלְלוּ אֶת־שֵׁם יְהוָה כִּי־נִשְׁגַּב שָׁמַי לְבָדוֹ הוֹדוּ עַל־אֲרֶץ וּשְׁמַיִם : וַיִּרְם קֶרֶן אֶלְעֲמוֹ תְהַלֵּה לְכָל־ חַסִּידָיו לְבְנֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל עִם־קָרְבוֹ הִלְלוּ־יְהוָה :</p>

Targum

Psa. 148:1 Hallelujah! Praise the LORD, holy creatures in Heaven; praise him, all hosts of angels on high. ² Praise him, all angels that minister in his presence; praise him, all his hosts. ³ Praise him, sun and moon; praise him, all stars of light. ⁴ Praise him, Heaven of heavens, and the waters that are suspended by his word above the heavens. ⁵ Let them praise the name of the LORD, for he commanded and they were created. ⁶ And he established them for ages upon ages; he gave a decree and none will violate it. ⁷ Praise the LORD in the Earth, sea serpents and all abysses. ⁸ Fire and hail, snow and vapor, storm wind fulfilling his command; ⁹ Mountains and all hills, [every] tree that produces fruit, and all cedars; ¹⁰ Animals and every beast, creeping things and the winged bird that flies; ¹¹ Kings of the Earth and all peoples; rulers and all judges of the Earth. ¹² Lads and even girls, old men and youths; ¹³ Let them praise the name of the LORD, for his name is mighty, he alone; his praise is over Earth and Heaven. ¹⁴ And he has lifted up glory for his people, praise for all his pious ones, for the children of Israel, the people who are close to him: Praise the LORD!

Interlinear

	Psa. 148:1	Praise		Praise		
	Key	H1984b		H3068		
	Lex	הָלַל		יהוה		
	PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun		
the	Lord	Praise	the	Lord	from	
	H3050	H1984b		H3068		
	יְהוָה	הָלַל		יהוה		
	Noun	Verb		Noun		
the	heavens	Praise	Him	in	the	heights
	H8064	H1984b				H4791
	שָׁמַיִם	הָלַל				מְרוֹם
	Noun	Verb				Noun
	Psa. 148:2	Praise	Him	all	His	
	Key	H1984b		H3605		
	Lex	הָלַל		כָּל		
	PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun		
angels	Praise	Him	all	His	hosts	
H4397	H1984b		H3605		H6635	
מַלְאָכַי	הָלַל		כָּל		צְבָא	
Noun	Verb		Noun		Noun	
	Psa. 148:3	Praise	Him	sun	and	moon
	Key	H1984b		H8121		H3394
	Lex	הָלַל		שֶׁמֶשׁ		יָרֵחַ
	PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun		Noun
Praise	Him	all	stars	of	light	
H1984b		H3605	H3556		H0216	
הָלַל		כָּל	כּוֹכָב		אוֹר	
Verb		Noun	Noun		Noun	
	Psa. 148:4	Praise	Him	highest		
	Key	H1984b		H8064		
	Lex	הָלַל		שָׁמַיִם		
	PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun		
heavens	And	the	waters	that	are	above

H8064	H4325
שָׁמַיִם	כִּימִים
Noun	Noun

above	the	heavens
H5921		H8064
עַל		שָׁמַיִם
Part.		Noun

Psa. 148:5	Let	them	praise	the	name	of	the
Key			H1984b		H8034		
Lex			הָלַל		שֵׁם		
PrtSpeech			Verb		Noun		

Lord	For	He	commanded	and	they	were	created
H3068			H6680				H1254a
יְהוָה			צִוָּה				בָּרָא
Noun			Verb				Verb

Psa. 148:6	He	has	also	established	them	forever
Key				H5975		H5703
Lex				עָמַד		עַד
PrtSpeech				Verb		Noun

and	ever	He	has	made	a	decree	which	will	not
	H5769			H5414		H2706			
	עוֹלָם			בָּתַן		חֶק			
	Noun			Verb		Noun			

pass	away
H5674a	H5674a
עָבַר	עָבַר
Verb	Verb

Psa. 148:7	Praise	the	Lord
Key	H1984b		H3068
Lex	הָלַל		יְהוָה
PrtSpeech	Verb		Noun

from	the	earth	Sea	monsters	and	all
		H0776	H8577	H8577		H3605
		אָרֶץ	תַּיִן	תַּיִן		כָּל
		Noun	Noun	Noun		Noun

deeps
H8415
תְּהוֹם
Noun

Psa. 148:8	Fire	and	hail
Key	H0784		H1259
Lex	אֵשׁ		בָּרָד
PrtSpeech	Noun		Noun

snow	and	clouds
H7950		H7008
שֶׁלֶג		קִיטוֹר
Noun		Noun

Stormy	wind	fulfilling	His	word
H5591b	H7307	H6213a		H1697
סְעָרָה	רוּחַ	עָשָׂה		דְּבָר
Noun	Noun	Verb		Noun

Psa. 148:9	Mountains	and	all
Key	H2022		H3605
Lex	הַר		כָּל
PrtSpeech	Noun		Noun

hills	Fruit	trees	and	all
H1389	H6529	H6086		H3605
גְּבֻעָה	פְּרִי	עֵץ		כָּל
Noun	Noun	Noun		Noun

cedars
H0730
אֲרִז
Noun

Psa. 148:10	Beasts	and	all
Key	H2421b		H3605
Lex	תַּיִה		כָּל
PrtSpeech	Noun		Noun

cattle	Creeping	things	and	winged
H0929	H7431	H7431		H3671
בְּהֵמָה	רֶמֶשׂ	רֶמֶשׂ		כְּנָף

Noun Noun Noun Noun

fowl
H6833
צֶפֶר
Noun

Psa. 148:11 Kings of the earth
Key H4428 H0776
Lex מְלִכִּים אֲרֶץ
PrtSpeech Noun Noun

and all peoples Princes and all judges of
H3605 H3816 H8269 H3605 H8199
כָּל לְאֻמֹּת שָׂרֵי כָּל שֹׁפְטֵי
Noun Noun Noun Noun Verb

the earth
H0776
אֲרֶץ
Noun

Psa. 148:12 Both young men and virgins
Key H0970 H0970 H1330
Lex בָּחֹרִים בָּחֹרִים בְּתוּלָה
PrtSpeech Noun Noun Noun

Old men and children
H2205 H2205 H5288
זָקֵן זָקֵן נָעַר
Adj. Adj. Noun

Psa. 148:13 Let them praise the
Key H1984b
Lex הִלְלֵי
PrtSpeech Verb

name of the Lord For His name alone is
H8034 H3068 H8034 H0905
שֵׁם יְהוָה שֵׁם בַּד
Noun Noun Noun Noun

exalted His glory is above earth and heaven

H7682 שָׁגַב Verb	H1935 הוֹדָה Noun	H5921 עָלָה Part.	H0776 אָרָץ Noun	H8064 שָׁמַיִם Noun					
Psa. 148:14 Key Lex PrtSpeech	And	He	has	lifted H7311 רוֹם Verb	up	a	horn H7161 קַרְנָן Noun	for	His
people H5971a עַם Noun	Praise H1984b הָלַל Verb	for	all H3605 כָּל Noun	His	godly H2623 הַסִּיד Adj.				
ones H2623 הַסִּיד Adj.	Even	for	the	sons H1121 בָּנִים Noun	of	Israel H3478 יִשְׂרָאֵל Noun	a		
people H5971a עַם Noun	near H7138 קָרוֹב Adj.	to	Him	Praise H1984b הָלַל Verb	the				
Lord H3050 יְהוָה Noun									

Summary of the Psalm

This Psalm speaks about when the Gentile nations of the world will receive the knowledge of the LORD. When this happens, the Universe, all living things, from the heights to low places, will come together in praise of the Creator. The Psalm concludes with the rise of Israel, which will guarantee to all people who dedicate themselves to the LORD that they will receive recognition from Heaven for their good deeds.

The LORD's creation is portrayed as two spheres. The Spiritual (celestial) sphere and the terrestrial sphere. Ancient people believed that the celestial sphere was the Heavens. In this sphere, everything was spiritual. On Earth, the LORD's creation is the material world. The terrestrial world will come together one day, Jews, Gentiles, and the creatures of the Earth, to sing a hymn of praise to the LORD as Creator, Preserver, and Lawgiver. The Gentiles will become a part of Israel through their good deeds and dedication to the LORD. All peoples and nations will become one people and one nation.

Verses One to Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Praise the LORD! Praise the LORD from the heavens; Praise Him in the heights!</p>	<p>תְּהַלְלוּ יְהוָה אֶת־יְהוָה מִן־ הַשָּׁמַיִם הַלְלוּהוּ בַמְרוֹמִים :</p>
<p>² Praise Him, all His angels; Praise Him, all His hosts!</p>	<p>הַלְלוּהוּ כָּל־מַלְאָכָיו הַלְלוּהוּ כָּל־</p>
<p>³ Praise Him, sun and moon; Praise Him, all stars of light!</p>	<p>הַלְלוּהוּ שֶׁמֶשׁ וְיָרֵחַ וְכָל־כּוֹכָבֵי אֹרֶךְ :</p>
<p>⁴ Praise Him, highest heavens, And the waters that are above the heavens!</p>	<p>הַשָּׁמַיִם הַגְּבוּהִים וְהַמַּיִם אֲשֶׁר־</p>
<p>⁵ Let them praise the name of the LORD, For He commanded and they were created.</p>	<p>יְהַלְלוּ אֶת־יְהוָה מֵעַל הַשָּׁמַיִם :</p>
<p>⁶ He has also established them forever and ever; He has made a decree which will not pass away.</p>	<p>וַיִּצְוֶה אֶת־יְהוָה לְעַד לְעוֹלָם חֶק־נֶתַן</p>
	<p>וְלֹא יִעָבֹר :</p>

Verse Analysis

מִן־הַשָּׁמַיִם (min hashamayim) means “from the Heavens.” The usage of שָׁמַיִם falls into two broad categories, 1) the physical heavens and 2) the heavens as the abode of God. In verse one, the Heavens are referring to the physical heavens and the creatures of the Heavens. The luminaries, sun, moon, and stars will join together with the angels and the Heavenly Host to give one considerable praise to the LORD. The celestial world is

something that is a mystery to humans. Yes, today, we do understand that the celestial bodies are a part of Malkhut (the physical realm). For ancient people, they did not understand this. For them, everything above the blue sky represented Heaven. The celestial world today is not a part of the spiritual world. The Sefirot Keter to Yesod are the Upper and Lower waters of the spiritual realm. All the Sefirot, the Hebrew Letters, the angels, and every spiritual entity praise the LORD. Our Ruach came from the Lower Waters of the Tree of Life, and one day each of us will return there to be a part of the spiritual world, which is in constant praise of the LORD.

כָּל-כּוֹכְבֵי אֹרֶן: (kal coc'ver ohr) – means “stars of light.” This phrase is referring to the fixed stars in the sky that project their light upon the Earth. The fixed stars are referred to as the luminaries.

וְהַמַּיִם אֲשֶׁר אֶמַעַל הַשָּׁמַיִם: (v'hamayim asher mel hashamayim) – means “the waters above the heavens.” This phrase indicates that the psalmist believed that there are worlds still being created today. These unknown bodies are still underwater, as was the Earth at the beginning of creation. The Sages have believed that the LORD's creation process has never stopped. It will continue throughout time. Galaxies are being formed and created even now. Stars explode, and new stars are born. The process of creation is a never-ending process.

In verse one, the psalmist reminds us that the celestial bodies are closely related to the LORD because they are a part of the Heavens. The creatures of Earth are far removed from the presence of the LORD because these things exist in the material world. However, the LORD's power and presence can be felt and seen in Malkhut. The

heavenly message from the LORD to humans can be heard by those who are devoted to serving the LORD and praise His holy name.

The bright stars of verse three are described in the Talmud (Bava Basra 8b) as elementary school teachers. Our youth depend on teachers for their education. Youth will learn about the LORD by having teachers. Parents are the best teachers for this purpose. The parents must teach their children about the LORD. If the LORD's teachings are not passed from one generation to another, in time, humankind will not know of the LORD. The LORD will always be present in Malkhut through His Light. Without people performing the Mitzvot of the Torah, then the blessings from Heaven will cease to come down from Yesod. The cycle of blessings is that the LORD sends them to Malkhut. People, in turn, share the blessing by performing the Mitzvot of the Torah. This act sends praises back to the LORD through Yesod. For each praise, the LORD returns blessings. As long as there are people devout to the LORD, the cycle of blessings will always continue.

In verse five, the psalmist reminds us of how important it is to remember that the LORD created the Tree of Life by uttering a few words. The LORD developed the complexity of the Tree of Life. A few words found in the first verses of Genesis, the ten Sefirot, the Hebrew letters, and all spiritual entities were created.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The English translation from the New American Standard is adequate for the spiritual awareness of this Psalm

Verses Seven to Fourteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>7 Praise the LORD from the Earth, Sea monsters and all deeps; 8 Fire and hail, snow and clouds; Stormy wind, fulfilling His word; 9 Mountains and all hills; Fruit trees and all cedars; 10 Beasts and all cattle; Creeping things and winged fowl; 11 Kings of the Earth and all peoples; Princes and all judges of the Earth; 12 Both young men and virgins; Old men and children.</p>	<p>7 הַלְלוּ אֶת־יְהוָה מִן־הָאָרֶץ תַּנְיִינִים וְכָל־תְּהוֹמוֹת׃ 8 אֵשׁ וּבָרָד שֶׁלֵּג וְקִיטּוֹר רוּחַ סְעָרָה עֹשֶׂה דְבָרוֹ׃ 9 הַהָרִים וְכָל־גְּבְעוֹת עֵץ פְּרִי וְכָל־ אֲרָזִים׃ 10 הַתְּיָה וְכָל־בְּהֵמָה רֹמֵשׁ וְצִפּוֹר כָּנָף׃ 11 מַלְכֵי־אָרֶץ וְכָל־ לְאֻמִּים שָׂרִים וְכָל־שֹׁפְטֵי אָרֶץ׃ 12 בַּתּוֹרִים וְגַם־בַּתּוֹלְוֹת זִקְנִים עִם־ נְעָרִים׃ 13 יְהַלְלוּ אֶת־שֵׁם יְהוָה כִּי־נִשְׁגַּב שָׁמַיִם לְבָדוֹ הוֹדוּ עַל־ אָרֶץ וּשְׁמַיִם׃ 14 וַיִּזְרַם קָרָן וּלְעֹמֹ תְהַלֵּה לְכָל־חֲסִידָיו לְבָנֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל עִם־קָרְבּוֹ הַלְלוּ־יְהוָה׃</p>
<p>13 Let them praise the name of the LORD, For His name alone is exalted; His glory is above Earth and Heaven. 14 And He has lifted up a horn for His people, Praise for all His godly ones; <i>Even</i> for the sons of Israel, a people near to Him. Praise the LORD!</p>	

Verses Analysis

קִיטּוֹר (keetor) – means “smoke.” In this Psalm, it is translated as clouds. Hirsch says that means “mist” or vapor.” If the word is understood as a mist, then it could be referring to fog. Thick fog and smoke give the same results. It is difficult and sometimes impossible to see through a fog.

Everything on Earth, in the realm of Malkhut, will praise the LORD. Some events happen in Malkhut that can cause destruction. Thunderstorms can burn down houses. Tornadoes can destroy crops. These events need to be viewed as the negative energy from the left column. Gevurah and Hod generate negative energy that is sent to Malkhut. Negative energy has its value in Malkhut. The world cannot exist without the three energies from the Tree of Life. Sadly negative energy can cause destruction. However, negative energy, for example, electricity, is a good thing. Humankind has to learn how to harness negative energy for its advantage. History tells us that humans have used negative energy to hurt and control each other. If too much negative energy accumulates within a person, the Klippot of evil can form. The brutal dictators of history all had the Klippot surrounding them. These people could not see that what they were doing was evil and against the LORD's decrees. It is next to impossible for positive energy alone to break through a Klippot. Eventually, dictators are overthrown. Unfortunately, it takes many resources to accomplish this.

Verse twelve connects young maidens and young men. Generally speaking, the young want to make themselves attractive to each other. Concentrating on the LORD's ways is easily made a minor consideration so that the young maiden and man can fall in love. During the days of the Messiah, even the young will turn away from their Nefesh's (the flesh) to dedicate themselves to praising and honoring the LORD. The young and the old will learn from each other how best to serve and praise the LORD.

Verse thirteen says that when the Messiah arrives and leads the world, the Kings and other persons in authority will give up their power. They will serve the Messiah, who will show all the world's peoples how to serve the LORD with praise and song.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The New American Standard has a reasonable translation of this section except for verse fourteen. Hirsch's translation offers a better view of the spiritual awareness of the verse.

14 And He lifted up the horn – the praiseworthy heights that Yisrael achieved – for His people, which in turn are praised by all those [of the nations] who are devoted to Him and who praise the children of Yisrael as the people who have been close to Him from the beginning: Halleluyah.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

